

WP2 Facilitate SNOMED CT use and raising awareness, sharing knowledge and training initiatives

D2.1 SNOMED CT awareness raising, education and training plan

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Executive Summary

The *Portugal SNOMED International membership 2* (SNO-PT 2) action will enable the expansion of the Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT)¹ coverage in Portugal, by renewing the status of SNOMED International membership which allows free distribution and use of this terminology within the Health System (public and private organisations) and other health-related entities.

The adoption of a standardized terminology for clinical and administrative concepts, like SNOMED CT ensures consistent understanding and interpretation of health information at national and cross border levels between different health systems, enhancing data quality and ultimately improving healthcare services for the public. To make stakeholders aware of the importance of using this terminology, the implementation of activities such as awareness raising, exploitation of objectives and outcomes and training are crucial.

Within the scope of *WP2 Facilitate SNOMED CT use and raising awareness, sharing knowledge and training initiatives*, this document defines a strategy to raise awareness of SNOMED CT and describes a plan to lay the foundation for the successful implementation of a variety of communication, dissemination and training activities.

The brand strategy created by the previous SNO-PT action and reinforced in SNO-PT 2 strengthened those efforts by creating a unified framework, including the definition of target groups and a clear vision, mission, and values, as well as the establishment of a distinct brand name and visual identity for these activities. This plan also includes the creation of a project webpage and standardized document templates to ensure uniform communication and professional presentations. It also offers a guide to ensure the correct use of the EU co-funding visibility rules by the different team members. Moreover, this document outlines the process for monitoring WP2 activities and achieving the indicators specified in the SNO-PT 2 Grant Agreement, ensuring a clear procedure for data collection and reporting.

Collectively, these resources guide SNO-PT 2 team members in implementing WP2 activities, with the overarching aim of raising awareness among end users about the major benefits of SNOMED CT and the impact of the SNO-PT 2 action.

¹ SNOMED International. *What is SNOMED CT*. [Available [here](#)]. Accessed in March 2025.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CTC	Clinical Terminologies Centre
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Record
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
IT	Information Techonology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator(s)
MS	Milestone(s)
NHS	National Health Service
NRC	National Release Centre
SNO-PT	Portugal SNOMED International membership
SNO-PT 2	Portugal SNOMED International membership 2
SPMS	SPMS – Serviços Partilhados do Ministério da Saúde, E.P.E. (Shared Services of Ministry of Health)
SNOMED CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms
WP	Work Package(s)

1. Introduction

The *Portugal SNOMED International membership 2* (SNO-PT 2) action will enable the expansion of the Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT) coverage in Portugal, by renewing the status of SNOMED International membership which allows free distribution and use of that terminology within the Health System (public and private organisations) and other health-related entities.

By fostering the adoption of SNOMED CT in Portugal, SNO-PT 2 seeks to reinforce the commitment of Portugal with semantic interoperability in healthcare information management, impacting national systems in a positive way and significantly contributing to the European Health Data Space (EHDS)². This facilitates the exchange of information between health systems, improving both national and cross-border care provision. Therefore, SNO-PT 2 is aligned with the overall EU strategy, that seeks to enable EU citizens to have their health data accessible in all Member States languages, promoting more effective communication and more personalized healthcare.

The semantic interoperability provided by SNOMED CT also drives significant advances in the field of medical research, innovation, health policies and regulatory activities. Therefore, SNO-PT 2 not only promotes efficiency and quality in the provision of healthcare (primary use of data) but also contributes to increase the quality of data available for secondary use, strengthening the knowledge base for scientific investigations, and driving advances in medicine and public health.

SNO-PT 2 action follows the *Portugal SNOMED International membership (SNO-PT)* action to further develop the results of the latter action and reinforce its strategy.

1.1. Scope

As stated in the SNO-PT 2 Grant Agreement (GA), the Work Package 2 (WP2) *Facilitate SNOMED CT use and raising awareness, sharing knowledge and training initiatives* refers to all communication and dissemination activities related to this action, that aim at communicating the results of SNOMED CT use through SNO-PT 2, as well as the ongoing national efforts. This WP also includes activities pertaining to results and use case dissemination (such as oral communications), participation in SNOMED International business meetings, and outreach and support initiatives for national partners.

WP2 includes two main tasks, Tasks 2.1 *Promote and facilitate the use of SNOMED CT* and T2.2 *Raising awareness, sharing knowledge and training initiative*, that have the following main goals:

² Regulation (EU) 2025/327 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 February 2025 on the European Health Data Space and amending Directive 2011/24/EU and Regulation (EU) 2024/2847 (Text with EEA relevance). [Available [here](#)]. Accessed in March 2025.

- Promote and facilitate the use of SNOMED CT terminology in national health-related organizations by providing support to these institutions when these start to employ SNOMED CT coded clinical terms and/or during expansion of the coded terms.
- Dissemination of SNOMED CT national initiatives through news publication in the dedicated project website.
- Participation in SNOMED CT official conferences and working groups.
- Provide training/support materials to stakeholders involved in the expansion of SNOMED CT use in health-related national organizations (e.g. support/training materials to stakeholders resulting from the ongoing initiatives in the scope of the use cases).

This document outlines the key principles of awareness raising, education and training for the SNO-PT 2 action, aiming to inform and educate citizens, healthcare professionals, health IT providers, policymakers, regulators, and the research community about the licensing, use, and benefits of SNOMED CT in the context of standardized clinical terminologies.

1.2. Objectives

This document describes the overall strategy of communication, dissemination and training activities of SNO-PT 2 in order to raise awareness and education around the usage of SNOMED CT, ensuring effective communication while maximizing the visibility of the project. This Plan will also serve as support to evaluate, monitor and report those activities.

The main objectives of this Deliverable are:

- To define a strategy to raise awareness of SNOMED CT
- To outline a plan for Dissemination, Communication and Training activities
- To design a method for monitoring WP2 activities

2. Strategy to raise awareness of SNOMED CT

The SNOMED CT awareness raising plan within the SNO-PT 2 action represents a strategic initiative aimed at maximising the visibility and impact of SNOMED CT adoption within the healthcare environment. Through a comprehensive set of activities, the plan aims to raise awareness, promote understanding, and facilitate the effective utilization of SNOMED CT among diverse stakeholders, ranging from policymakers and healthcare professionals to researchers and industry representatives.

Crafting an effective dissemination and outreach plan is a core goal of WP2. The plan focuses on identifying target audiences, creating a branding strategy, and fostering stakeholder engagement, which are designed to foster SNOMED CT adoption and expansion in Portugal.

This plan includes the development of promotional materials such as a project webpage, templates for presentations and other dissemination materials, all designed to convey key messages and project achievements in alignment with visual identity of SNO-PT 2, while highlighting the relevance and benefits of the SNOMED CT usage.

The overall vision underlying the awareness raising, training and education strategy aims to accomplish the following objectives:

- Make users and the diverse stakeholder groups aware of the project and the current developments.
- Facilitate adoption of SNOMED CT terminologies.
- Drive the effective utilization of standardized clinical terminologies within the Portuguese health system.

2.1. Target Groups

WP2 communication activities are strategically designed to have a high impact and visibility among key stakeholders. These efforts aim to align the SNO-PT 2 action with national objectives and principles as well as of the European Health Data Space (EHDS)² regulation, fostering collaboration and data sharing within and across borders.

The target groups of SNO-PT 2 are the same as those reported in SNO-PT action, following the same objectives of maintaining and exploiting the use of SNOMED CT in healthcare information systems by healthcare institutions and health-related entities at national level.

The target audience of SNO-PT 2 includes various stakeholders within the health system and health-related entities, such as:

- **Healthcare Professionals:** Including doctors, nurses, pharmacists, and other clinicians who interact with clinical data on a daily basis. These individuals benefit from standardised clinical terminologies like SNOMED CT, which facilitate clear communication and accurate documentation of patient information.
- **Healthcare entities:** Such as hospitals, clinics, laboratories, and healthcare facilities that manage patient records and medical data. Standardised clinical

terminologies enhance interoperability between different healthcare systems and support the seamless exchange of information.

- **Health Information Technology (IT) Providers:** Companies and organisations that develop and implement healthcare information technology solutions. These providers play a critical role in integrating standardised clinical terminologies into Electronic Health Records (EHR) and other health IT systems.
- **Policymakers and Regulators:** National and regional authorities responsible for healthcare policies formulation, regulation, and oversight. These stakeholders are interested in promoting the adoption of standardised terminologies to improve healthcare quality, safety, and efficiency.
- **Research Community:** Academic institutions, researchers, and scientists conducting studies in healthcare informatics, epidemiology, and clinical research. Standardised clinical terminologies support data harmonisation and facilitate secondary use of health data for research purposes.
- **Patients:** Individuals seeking access to high-quality healthcare services and advocating for patient-centred care. While not directly involved in the implementation of standardised terminologies, patients benefit from improved healthcare communication and information exchange enabled by initiatives like SNO-PT 2.

2.2. SNO-PT 2 Brand strategy

The dissemination and outreach activities of SNO-PT 2 need to be supported by a robust brand identity, ensuring the project remains prominent among key target audience. To reinforce this identity, the comprehensive visual style guide developed by SNO-PT to standardize the tone and presentation of all communication and outreach efforts was adopted by SNO-PT 2, as this action is a continuity of that previous one and so, principles, vision, mission, values and brand are identical. Some changes were done to adequate those characteristics to this new action, whenever appropriated. The next subsections outline the project vision, mission, and brand and visual identity.

2.2.1. Vision, Mission and Value

Defining a vision, mission and value is essential for establishing direction and focus, which are critical to the development and successful execution of this plan. The vision of a project defines the long-term impact it seeks to achieve, while the mission describes the project purpose and outlines the approach the project will take to fulfil that vision. Moreover, value helps to communicate the impact, investment and benefits that SNO-PT 2 aims to achieved. Together, these elements help to align stakeholders, drive decision making processes, and enhance communication, dissemination and training activities³. These statements are the same as the ones of SNO-PT as SNO-PT 2 follows the principles of the

³ Foster, D. (2024, May 3). *Vision, mission and values: How they differ and why they matter*. Forbes. [Available [here](#)]. Accessed in April 2025.

previous action. Table 1 describes the vision, mission and value statements of SNO-PT 2 action.

Table 1. SNO-PT 2 Vision, Mission and Value statements

Vision	To lead the advancement of healthcare interoperability in Portugal by fostering the widespread adoption of standardized health terminologies, like SNOMED CT, to ensure improved patient outcomes and contributing to the development of the European Health Data Space (EHDS).
Mission	To support the renewal of SNOMED International membership fee through EU co-financing enabling the free access and distribution of its international standardized terminology (SNOMED CT) in Portugal. By managing semantic health catalogues and integrating international classifications, SNO-PT 2 aims to enhance primary and secondary uses of health data, supporting better healthcare delivery, innovative research, policies development and regulatory activities.
Value	To empower healthcare innovation and interoperability in Portugal by providing free access to SNOMED CT, allowing the seamless exchange of health information, improving patient care at national and cross-border levels, as well as improving advancing medical research and policymaking through standardized, high-quality health data.

2.2.2. Brand name and Visual identity

The full name of the action is “Portugal SNOMED International membership 2” which will be used at the beginning of all raising awareness, communication, dissemination and training materials. The “2” means that this is the second action following the same objectives and outcomes as defined in SNO-PT. Following this, the official acronym SNO-PT 2 may be used in subsequent references.

A strong brand image is relevant to align it with the goals of the project. Therefore, the SNO-PT 2 visual identity was established, which incorporates specific elements (logos, colours, and templates) intended for consistent use across all dissemination materials.

The SNO-PT 2 logo is composed of three distinct graphic elements: the symbol, the acronym and the full name, as in Figure 1, also based on SNO-PT logo to provide the idea of continuity.

Figure 1. SNO-PT 2 Logo

The symbol of the SNO-PT 2 action features a book and a magnifying glass, symbolizing the emphasis of the action on the international clinical terminology SNOMED CT, used in healthcare clinical and administrative contexts.

In the context of the SNO-PT 2 action, the book represents the extensive clinical coverage of standardized terminology SNOMED CT. Additionally, it symbolises the catalogues used to report and store terminologies for several clinical areas, as documented in the Centre for Clinical Terminologies (CTC) catalogues⁴. These catalogues are essential to ensure the documentation of the terminologies available and used by each category and attributes across multiple clinical domains.

The magnifying glass symbolizes examination, scrutiny, and detailed analysis. Within the SNO-PT 2 action, it means the exploration and utilization of SNOMED CT to enhance healthcare and administrative practices, especially in the context of Electronic Health Record (EHR) management, storage and exchange.

Collectively, the book and magnifying glass in the SNO-PT 2 action logo underscore a commitment to leveraging SNOMED CT as a data standardization resource for healthcare professionals, researchers, and other end users. This resource enables them to access, analyse, and apply clinical terminology effectively in healthcare and administrative settings.

The selection of blue and white hues for the SNO-PT 2 logo aims to evoke feelings of trust, and integrity. These colours align with the objective of the action to expand the use of SNOMED CT clinical terminology to improve healthcare practices and systems. The primary colour of the logo – blue – was chosen for its associations with health, trust, and unity. In colour psychology, blue is often linked to feelings of trust, stability, relaxation and confidence⁵. Globally, these colours hues reflect the commitment of the action with robust and sustainable healthcare solutions.

Moreover, the SNO-PT 2 palette of colours (Figure 2) aligns with SNOMED CT image, ensuring a cohesive visual identify for the brand.

Together, these colours contribute to the visual identity of SNO-PT 2, reinforcing its mission to advance healthcare practices through the effective utilization of SNOMED CT.

	RGB: 255, 255, 255	Hex: FFFFFFFF
	RGB: 100, 192, 222	Hex: #64C0DE
	RGB: 0, 56, 101	Hex: #003865
	RGB: 4, 61, 106	Hex: #043D6A

Figure 2. SNO-PT 2 Brand colours

⁴ Centre for Clinical Terminologies. *Catalogs*. [Available [here](#)]. Accessed in October 2024.

⁵ T. M. Maghraby, A. E. Elhag, R. M. Romeh, D. M. Elhawary, and A. G. Hassabo, 'The Psychology of Color and Its Effect on Branding', *Journal of Textiles, Coloration and Polymer Science*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 1–9, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.21608/jtcps.2024.259014.1270.

There is also another logo that can be applied to some specific situations, if appropriated, due to the background colours, as shown in Figure 3. The same principles, colours and visibility described above also apply to this one.

Figure 3. SNO-PT 2 Alternative logo

2.2.3. EU Co-Funded Rules

This action (SNO-PT 2) is co-funded by the European Union (EU) and according to its GA, article 17, all communication and dissemination activities must acknowledge the EU funding. This includes displaying the EU flag and the funding statement. Therefore, the following flags and statements (Table 2), in English and Portuguese, have been elaborated to comply with this rule, which must be included in all materials produced for SNO-PT 2.

Table 2. EU Co-funded flag and Disclaimer

EU Flag	Disclaimer
<p>Co-funded by the European Union</p>	<p>The SNO-PT 2 action is co-funded by the European Union, EU4Health Programme 2021-2027 under the Grant Agreement Nr 101181370. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.</p>
<p>Cofinanciado pela União Europeia</p>	<p>A ação SNO-PT 2 é cofinanciado pela União Europeia, EU4Health Programme 2021-2027 ao abrigo do <i>Grant Agreement</i> (Acordo de Subvenção) Nº 101181370. No entanto, os pontos de vista e opiniões expressos são exclusivamente da responsabilidade do(s) autor(es) e não refletem necessariamente os da União Europeia ou da Agência Europeia de Execução para a Saúde e o Digital (<i>European Health and Digital Executive Agency, HaDEA</i>). Nem a União Europeia nem a entidade financiadora podem ser responsabilizados por esses pontos de vista ou opiniões.</p>

2.2.4. Templates

To ensure consistency and professionalism across all communication materials, templates were developed for the SNO-PT 2 deliverables and presentations in Microsoft Word and Microsoft PowerPoint, respectively. These templates include the action logo, brand name, action title, official logos of SPMS and the EU co-funding logo and disclaimer. They were designed in compliance with the visual identity of the action and colour scheme, reinforcing brand recognition and cohesion.

These templates are stored in the SharePoint of the action to ensure easy access to SNO-PT 2 team members. When needed, team members can easily access these templates,

enabling them to maintain a unified visual presence across various communication channels, such as internal meetings and external events, whenever applicable.

2.2.4.1. Deliverables

All deliverables and milestones identified as reports in the GA will be produced using the official SNO-PT 2 Word template. The cover page of this template (as seen in this document) contains the following elements:

- Logo of the action.
- Acronym.
- Full action title.
- Identification of the WP (WP number & title).
- Document title (e.g., Deliverable number and title).
- Table with informative information related to the document (project coordinator, start date of the action and duration, status, version, dissemination level, main author(s), delivery date, due date – GA deadline – and deliverable type).
- Disclaimer of the project.
- European Union co-funding logo.
- Left border column with the symbols of SNO-PT 2 (book and magnifying glass).

In the remaining of the document, the header is constituted by the logo of the project along with the title of the document, its version, and correspondent date. In the footer, the European co-funding logo, full action name and page number are provided.

Styles for headings, table of contents, text, and other elements were created to ensure consistency and simplify the process of document quality review by the coordination team.

The Deliverable template comprises also a back cover, containing the logo, the action webpage, the disclaimer and the EU flag and a left border column with the symbols of SNO-PT 2 (book and magnifying glass), as in the cover page making it even more personalised.

2.2.4.2. Presentations

A specific template to elaborate presentations related to the SNO-PT 2 was created, using PowerPoint. To be in line with the specifications described in the previous sub-sections, the cover and last slides of the presentations are identified with logo and full action title, as well as the EU co-funded logo along with the disclaimer in the last slide of the presentation, as shown in Figure 4 and Figure 7. The remaining slides of the presentation feature a footer displaying the relevant logos along with the copyright statement and slide number (Figure 5 and Figure 6). The institutional logos of SPMS are also included to ensure compliance with institutional guidelines.

Figure 4. SNO-PT 2 Presentation cover page

Figure 5. SNO-PT 2 Presentation slide

Figure 6. SNO-PT 2 Middle title slide

Figure 7. SNO-PT 2 Presentation last slide

2.3. Webpage

The SNO-PT 2 webpage is part of the CTC website (<https://www.ctc.min-saude.pt/projetos-cofinanciados/>) which is described in detail in D2.2 *Project Website*. This webpage serves as the main platform for disseminating key updates regarding the renewal of the SNOMED International membership fee of Portugal, supported by co-funding from the EU4Health 2021 – 2027 programme.

This page follows the SNO-PT principles, providing information on the objectives, indicators, news, results (public deliverables, dissemination and educational materials, etc.) and progress of the action. Information regarding the previous action (SNO-PT) is also maintained on the same webpage, highlighting the results of the latter and the continuity of activities through action SNO-PT 2, including a continuous timeline of the two actions.

Annex I describes a proposal for the webpage structure and respective content. The text of the webpage can be seen in English (EN) or Portuguese (PT). Text language can be interchanged by clicking in the icon on the right side of the menu, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. CTC menu languages

The explanatory text includes a figure (Figure 9) showing the relevance of SNOMED CT for the interoperability and communication among health systems, support to digital health and standardisation of clinical data, improving healthcare delivery while supporting medical research and innovation for secondary use of data and a more efficient management of health resources which can contribute to the sustainability and better efficiency of National Health Service (NHS) management.

Figure 9. SNOMED CT benefits for digital health image proposal

3. Activities Plan

A communication and dissemination plan plays a crucial role in efficiently managing efforts to ensure that the SNO-PT 2 objectives, results and impact are effectively communicated to the relevant target groups. This plan aims to raise awareness of SNO-PT 2 action and increase its visibility, engage stakeholders, and ensure that the action outputs are effectively disseminated to pertinent stakeholders, maximising its overall impact.

This section is organized into three main subsections: Dissemination, Communication and Training activities. This plan can be adjusted throughout the action according to the CTC activities and the availability of services and catalogues that depend on external factors to this action.

3.1. Dissemination

Dissemination refers to the activities conducted for providing information and results to a broader audience, with the primary goal of raising awareness and ensuring that key findings or resources of SNO-PT 2 are accessible to those who need them. Its main goal is to make information and findings accessible to target audiences, including the general public, experts, decision-makers, and health-related organizations.

The webpage will be used as the primary channel for disseminating the project activities. It will feature the project objectives, SNOMED CT benefits, updates about important outcomes of this action, as well as relevant news, such as the beginning of the action and final outcomes achieved. The news will also be published using the social media channels of the SNO-PT 2 coordinator, leveraging the existing user base for a broader reach.

Overall, outreach activities will contribute to highlighting the use of EU-funded resources and how they can contribute to raising awareness about the importance of SNOMED CT in healthcare systems at national level and across borders.

3.2. Communication

Communication refers to the activities designed to promote engagement, build connections, and enable continuous discussion between the project team and different stakeholders. It emphasizes the efforts to engage audiences, shaping perceptions and encouraging SNOMED CT adoption.

During the SNO-PT 2 action duration, at least one communication will be delivered by key elements of SPMS, focusing on the use and application of SNOMED CT in Portugal. This will be highly relevant to showcase SNOMED CT benefits and applicability and promote overall awareness.

3.3. Training

Throughout the duration of the project, at least one training activity will be organized to provide support to national partners on the implementation of new use cases envisioned in this action to ensure that stakeholders and internal teams, are well-equipped to effectively use and apply SNOMED CT in their daily work. This activity aims to promote understanding, improve data accuracy, and foster the widespread adoption of this standardized health terminology. The training activities are closely aligned with the action goals of improving health data interoperability and ensuring the successful integration of SNOMED CT across different sectors.

4. Monitorization of WP2 activities

The monitorization of dissemination, communication and training activities represents an important step for the SNO-PT 2 action, not only to assess the overall impact of those activities but also to accomplish several key performance indicators (KPI) of this action. The activities proposed in this plan should be regularly evaluated using metrics and performance indicators, as previewed in the GA. By this way, it will be possible to identify which activities are producing more contribution on the sharing of knowledge among the target groups, or which activities will need to be adjusted to increase their value among the community.

Table 3 shows the set of KPI stated on the GA that serve as a guideline to monitor the WP2 activities. These Indicators have been reviewed by the involved teams to agree on the procedure to collect data, frequency of delivery, and data analysis, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. WP2 Indicators

KPI #	Description	Target (GA)	Evidence	Frequency of report
5	List of SNOMED CT official conferences and working groups, where MS have participated	6 SNOMED CT official business meetings (2 per year) and meetings of the EU Member Forum Work Group. 1 communication , showcasing the national advances / initiatives on SNOMED CT use at national level	Any public information like dissemination material, link, video, etc., number of participants per gender	Quarterly
6	List of national SNOMED CT education, promotion and training initiatives	1 support/training initiative is expected to be provided to national stakeholders during the duration of SNO-PT 2, to provide support to national partners on the implementation of the new use cases envisioned in this project.	Dissemination of the initiative (publicity, news, photos, etc.)	Quarterly

The SNO-PT 2 Project Manager and CTC Project Manager responsible for the distribution of SNOMED CT licenses and dissemination and training activities will work in close collaboration, meeting regularly to align the work and collect the needed information on activities and indicators to accomplish the objectives of the action.

The collected data will be used to elaborate cumulative yearly reports, as outlined in Milestones 4 (*Dissemination Report: Year 1*) and 5 (*Dissemination Report: Year 2*) and Deliverable 2.3 (*Dissemination Report: Final*). These reports will also contribute to the official Periodic Reports (PR) on technical and financial activities (Table 4). All evidence of

the activities conducted in WP2 will be archived in the working platforms of this action (SharePoint and Confluence).

Table 4. Cumulative Dissemination Reports

Report (Deliverable / Milestone)	Due Date	Corresponding Periodic Report
MS4 Dissemination Report: Year 1	2026-02-28	PR1
MS5 Dissemination Report: Year 2	2027-02-28	PR1
D2.3 Dissemination Report: Final	2027-12-31	PR2

Notes:

- **PR1:** from M1 till M24 (Jan 2025 – Dec 2026)
- **PR2:** from M25 till M36 (Jan 2027 – Dec 2027)

5. Conclusions

The use of SNOMED CT is fundamental for the standardisation of information in the health ecosystem which contributes significantly for the quality of healthcare delivery (primary use of data) and research and regulatory activities (secondary use of data).

This plan for awareness raising, education and training activities is important to guide the dissemination and communication of key information and building capacity to support the adoption and use of SNOMED CT in Portugal. It is also relevant to guide all involved teams in the execution of SNO-PT 2 ensuring that all rules of co-funding are applied and complied.

Moreover, the previewed development of a dedicated webpage is essential to raise awareness among end users about the major benefits of SNOMED CT and the impact of the SNO-PT 2 action.

Annexes

Annex I. Webpage structure proposal

Section	Description
Opening	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This webpage is under CTC site, menu SNOMED-CT, option “Co-financed projects”, dedicated to providing information regarding EU-funding projects. • A timeline showing the SNO-PT duration followed by SNO-PT 2 is shown. • The logo of SNO-PT 2 is shown clearly followed by a bottom “Learn more” from which additional information can be accessed. The same applies to SNO-PT action which is on the right side. • Below, there are the EU-Co-funding flags in English and Portuguese.
Specific SNO-PT 2 webpage structure	
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This section aims to outline the main goals of the action, scope, impact for the National Health Service (NHS). • The text can be consulted in Portuguese and English.
News	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This section aims to include news about the action, that can be delivered during its duration
Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This section aims to present the key results of SNO-PT 2, using clear and accessible language for a general audience
Disclaimer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The webpage ends with the official disclaimer and EU flag in line with the rules explained in section 2.2.3. and Table 2.

Annex II. Templates to report

The following sections show the templates created to collect information on dissemination, communication and training activities carried out in the context of the SNO-PT 2 action. These templates were designed based on the information required of the EC portal (Funding and Tenders), to facilitate the regular reporting process. Additionally, some qualitative data is collected to report the activities done during the SNO-PT 2 action period.

Some topics have a predefined list to choose (single or multiple choice), as shown below.

(1) Type of dissemination activity has the following **choice list** associated with it.

- Clustering activities
- Collaboration with EU-funded projects
- Conferences
- Education and training events
- Meetings
- Other
- Other scientific collaboration

(2) Target audience reached has the following **multiple choices** associated with it. It applies to **Dissemination and Communication** activities

- Industry, business partners
- Innovators
- Investors
- EU Institutions
- National authorities
- Regional authorities
- Local authorities
- Civil society
- Citizens
- Research communities
- Specific end user communities
- International organization (UN body, OECD, etc.)
- Other
- Investors

(3) Status of the activity has the following **choice list**. It applies to **Dissemination and Communication** activities.

- Cancelled
- Delivered
- Ongoing
- Postponed

(4) Communication channel has the following **choice list**.

- Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)
- Exhibition
- Interview
- Media article
- Newsletter
- Press release
- Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.)
- Social media
- TV / Radio campaign
- Video
- Website
- Other

(5) Country. List of Countries. It applies to **Training** activities.

Annex II.1. Dissemination activities

Date	Dissemination activity name	What? Type of dissemination activity ⁽¹⁾	Who? Target audience reached ⁽²⁾	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Evidence	Status of the dissemination activity ⁽³⁾
YYYY-MM-DD						

Annex II.2. Communication activities

Date	Communication activity name	Description	Who? Target audience reached ⁽²⁾	How? Communication channel ⁽⁴⁾	Outcome	Status ⁽³⁾
YYYY-MM-DD						

Annex II.3. Training activities

Date	Participant Legal name	Description of the training						Attendees (number per gender)		
		Name	Type	Area	City	Country	Duration (days)	Male	Female	Non-binary
YYYY-MM-DD	SPMS (PIC)									

For more information:

<https://www.ctc.min-saude.pt/projetos-cofinanciados/>

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